

**EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS AND COMPUTER SIMULATION
OF RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING
THROUGH MULTILAYER FIBER REINFORCEMENTS**

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ABSTRACT

Computer simulations of the filling process in resin transfer molding have been performed so far by various numerical techniques: finite difference, control volume, finite elements and boundary element method. Up till now two-dimensional or three-dimensional analysis have been limited mostly to solving Darcy's equation when the preform consists of one layer of fiber mats or woven rovings. Numerical simulations through several layers of fiber beds with highly contrasted permeabilities would require to discretize the porous medium into a very large number of geometrical elements, thus increasing considerably the computer time necessary to perform a mold filling analysis. This paper proposes a simple algorithm based on resin mass conservation to simulate the filling of multilayer porous media. It is designed to be coupled at each time step with a standard two-dimensional analysis. First, experimental results are presented which permit to observe the resin flow pattern through a multilayer fibrous reinforcement. Then, in order to assess the validity of this approach, preliminary numerical simulations are carried out for a simple model problem consisting of a two layers preform.

Key words: Resin Transfer Molding, numerical simulation, multilayer fiber reinforcement

1. INTRODUCTION

Numerical simulations of mold filling inside complex three-dimensional molds can become very computer intensive. When the progression of the resin front must be followed accurately, it is not uncommon to use a mesh containing several thousand elements. Since Darcy's equation must be solved numerically at each time step, this implies solving several large linear systems of simultaneous equations. Nevertheless, most if the analysis performed so far with the finite element program RTMFLOT [1] have remained quite feasible with an average processing time on a RISC/6000 workstation not exceeding one hour. The numerical procedure, which employs non-conforming finite elements on a fixed grid [2,3,4], has brought a significant gain in

performance over a previous method based on boundary-fitted finite differences on a moving mesh [5]. However, in the case of multilayer preforms, when 3 to 7 layers of fibrous beds are stacked in the mold, the numerical complexity of a full three-dimensional analysis well exceeds the practical capabilities of most affordable computers. One possibility would be to reduce the three-dimensional problem to a two-dimensional one by using a mathematical technique called homogenization [6]. But this method, apart from being mathematically complex, is limited to periodic fibrous media. Another technique employed by most investigators [7] consists in evaluating an average permeability on the thickness of the mold. Then a standard two-dimensional analysis is performed. Several averaging processes have been proposed so far to compute an equivalent permeability [7]. But none appear yet to yield better results. Moreover, the resin front obtained is an average one. The simulation does not permit to reproduce the preferential resin flow through high permeability layers as experimentally observed in Figure 3 for instance.

The purpose of this paper is to present an alternative approach. An average permeability is computed where it can safely be evaluated, namely some distance upstream from the flow front in the resin saturated part of the mold. The impregnation process through layers of different permeabilities is then followed by a simple algorithm based on resin mass conservation, which can be coupled at each time step with a standard two-dimensional analysis. Section 2 describes the experimental technique devised to observe the preferential impregnation in multilayer fibrous beds. Then in section 3, a model problem is studied numerically to assess the validity of this approach. Finally, the algorithm is briefly presented in section 4. Comparisons of numerical results with experimental resin front profiles remain to be performed.

2. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

The experiment reported has been carried out in order to investigate how series of fiber mats and woven rovings of different permeabilities stacked inside a mold influence the profile of the resin flow along the thickness of the part. In order to detect the shape of the flow front, thermistors have been inserted between the layers of the preform.

2.1 Experimental set-up

The mold is composed of a $\frac{1}{4}$ " steel plate for its base part and is covered by a $\frac{1}{2}$ " polycarbonate plate. The thickness of the cavity is $\frac{3}{8}$ ". Figure 1 shows a schematic of the mold, with the two injection ports A and B located respectively on the top wall of the mold and on the mold boundary. The positions of the resin front is detected by using two stacks of thermistors, piles #1 and #2, the locations of which is indicated in Figure 1. The thermistors are piled up in two series of 5 units at 32 cm and 42 cm from injection gate A. Figure 2 describes the stacking sequence of rovings and mats used for this experiment, namely 4 rovings J.B. MARTIN 1004 surrounded from above and below by 4 OCF 8610 fiber mats. It indicates also the vertical positions of the thermistors of each pile. Note that the wires of the thermistors have been laid so as to minimize perturbations to the flow.

2.2 Data acquisition

The signal from the thermistors is transmitted to a 80386 micro-computer via a multiplexer. When the resin, which has been heated just before the experiment, comes in contact with the thermistor, a rapid change in voltage occurs which permits to detect accurately the progression of the resin flow.

2.3 Experiment

Once the mold is closed, it is compressed and resin is injected from injection gate A with a constant pressure of 100 psi at the outflow of the pump. The resin viscosity was 75 cps and the measured flow rate 6.1 liters/min . The profiles of the resin flow detected by the two piles of thermistors are shown in Figure 3 for the half thickness of the mold. It is interesting to notice that in this experiment the delay of the resin front in the middle layer, i.e., for the woven rovings, tends to increase with time as the front moves further apart from the injection port. Although this phenomenon is complex since it is rather difficult to measure during impregnation the vertical flow rate between two layers of radically different reinforcements, it will be shown in the next section that a model based on Darcy's law can reproduce the experimental shape of the resin front.

3. NUMERICAL EXPERIMENT FOR A MODEL PROBLEM

The resin flow through anisotropic porous reinforcements has been successfully modeled by Darcy's law, which states that the resin velocity vector V is proportional to the gradient of the pressure field p

$$V = - \frac{[k]}{\mu} \nabla p \quad (1)$$

where $[k]$ is the permeability tensor and μ the resin viscosity. In the model problem studied here, Darcy's equation will be solved inside a vertical section of the mold. Since the resin profiles observed in the previous experiment are symmetrical across the thickness of the mold, only two layers of different permeabilities need to be considered. The model problem represented in Figure 4 consists of two layers of equal thickness and of permeabilities K_1 , K_2 for the upper and lower parts respectively, with $K_1 = 5 K_2$. The flow rate imposed on the left wall was $Q_0 = 50 \text{ cm}^3/\text{s}$. The normal derivatives of the pressure field vanish on the top and bottom walls, i.e., there is no flow through the mold boundary.

A finite element analysis of mold filling inside a vertical section of a rectangular cavity was carried out. The computed resin front profiles shown in Figure 4 reproduce correctly the shape of the flow front. Note that for a constant pressure imposed on the left wall, an identical shape of resin front profiles would be obtained, although the computed times would differ. The pressure field displayed in Figure 5 shows that the flow is uniform at some distance upstream from the resin front, namely where the isobars become vertical straight lines. Note that the same observation was made by Fracchia [8] after studying both experimentally and numerically flows through multilayer porous media. Therefore, it is conceptually possible to simulate mold filling by a simple two-dimensional model some distance upstream from the resin front and to use a different model in the vicinity of the resin front. In the next section, a simple algorithm is proposed to model the progression of the resin front through multilayer fiber reinforcements.

4. ALGORITHM TO MODEL THE PROGRESSION OF THE RESIN FRONT

The algorithm described here to model the progression of the resin front through a multilayer fiber preform is based on the conservation of the resin mass. A vertical section of the mold is decomposed into a finite number of rectangular cells as shown in Figure 6. Each layer may have

a different thickness, denoted by $H(i)$ for layer i . The total flow rate across the vertical left side is denoted by Q_t at time t . It is natural to assume that Q_t is divided into each layer proportionally to the thickness $H(i)$ and the permeability $K(i)$ of the layer. The following equation gives the flow rate $Q(i)$ through each layer

$$Q(i) = \frac{Q_t K(i) H(i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N K(i) H(i)} \quad (2)$$

where N is the total number of layers. Hence the total volume of resin injected in layer i during a time increment Δt is $Q(i) \Delta t$. Let $S(m)$ denote the base area of a vertical stack of cells (see Figure 6). If $M(i)$ is the total number of cells completely filled in each layer, then the total wet area of layer i that is in contact with an upper or a lower layer in the stack can be approximated by

$$A(i) = \sum_{m=1}^{M(i)} S(m) \quad (3)$$

Note that the area of the last cell that might contain some resin is neglected because it is not completely filled. In fact, all the resin flowing through a layer does not necessarily remain in this layer. Some vertical resin transfer exists from one layer to a neighboring one. The simplest way to assess this resin transfer is by assuming it to be proportional to the difference between the total wet areas of two adjacent layers

$$F(i, i-1) = T(i, i-1) [A(i-1) - A(i)] \quad (4)$$

where the factor of proportionality $T(i, i-1)$ called "transverse transfer coefficient" depends on the ratio of the permeabilities of two adjacent layers. If $A(i) \geq A(i-1)$, the transfer $F(i, i-1)$ is negative and corresponds to a net loss of resin from layer i to layer $i-1$. Conversely, when $A(i) < A(i-1)$, then layer i will gain a volume $F(i, i-1)$ of resin at the expense of layer $i-1$.

For each layer of reinforcement, it is possible to modify the estimated volume of resin $Q(i)$ as follows:

$$Q(i) \Delta t = Q(i) \Delta t + F(i, i+1) + F(i, i-1) \quad (5)$$

The number of cells $M(i)$ completely filled up of resin in layer i at time $t + \Delta t$ will then be modified accordingly.

The numerical values of $T(i, i-1)$ will be assessed by a numerical experiment as illustrated in figure 4. Two layers of equal thickness and of permeabilities K_1 , K_2 respectively are considered in the vertical section of a rectangular mold. The algorithm is implemented for the same model problem and a value of $T(1,2)$ is identified which yields the best approximation of resin front profiles as calculated by Darcy's equation (see Figure 4 for example). Note that if an experimental installation as described in section 2 is available, then the same identification procedure can be applied to estimate $T(1,2)$ such that the resin front profiles obtained by the algorithm will best approximate the experimental results (see Figure 3 for example). It was possible to verify that the algorithm permits to reproduce the experimental shape of the flow front as indicated in Figure 6.

5. CONCLUSION

The method proposed in this paper is an attempt to construct a feasible model of a very complex physical phenomenon: the filling of a shell type three-dimensional mold with multilayer fibrous reinforcement. It was shown experimentally that the resin front profile is not uniform across the thickness of the mold. However, it was possible to reproduce the shapes of the resin front by a two-dimensional finite element analysis based on Darcy's law. By examining the pressure field, it was observed on the numerical result that some distance upstream from the resin front the pressure is constant across the thickness of the mold. Therefore a full three-dimensional analysis is not necessary in the whole geometrical domain. At each time step a two-dimensional analysis can be carried out in the resin saturated part of the mold, coupled with a simple algorithm based on resin mass conservation in the vicinity of the flow front. A numerical "transverse transfer coefficient" characterizes the interface between two adjacent layers and depends on their relative permeabilities. It must be identified either by a numerical or a laboratory experiment. The proposed methodology remains to be validated by comparing experimental and numerical flow patterns. If the results are satisfactory, it can provide a simple and effective way to simulate the complex phenomenon of mold filling through multilayer fiber reinforcements.

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Figure 1. Schematic of the experimental mold.

Figure 2. Stacking sequence of the multilayer fibrous reinforcement and positions of the thermistors.

Figure 3. Experimental resin front profiles across the half thickness of the mold.

Figure 4. Calculated resin front profiles inside a vertical section of a rectangular cavity containing two layers of fiber reinforcement.

Figure 5. Pressure field during mold filling in the cavity containing two layers of fiber reinforcement.

Figure 6. Schematic of the algorithm used to model the progression of the resin front.